

Results and discussion

The analytical and spectroscopic results (Tables 1–5) showed that all complexes are mononuclear with general formula, $[\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{L-L}(\text{NO}_3)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where L-L = NBU, NBT, NBH_2 and NBH_A). All the complexes are yellow coloured solids and are stable at room temperature. These are soluble in DMSO and DMF. The complexes do not have sharp melting points and decompose above 280 °C.

IR spectral studies :

To study the binding mode of *N*-benzoyl urea and related ligands with uranium in the peroxo complexes, the IR spectra of the free ligands were compared with those of corresponding metal complexes. The IR spectra of all the complexes (Table 2) show three vibrational bands around 890–906, 643–682 and 441–469 cm^{-1} , assigned to $\nu(\text{O-O})$ intra stretching, asymmetric UO_2 stretch-

Table 1. Analytical data and some physical properties of peroxouranium(VI) complexes

Complex	Empirical formula (Mol. wt.) (g mol ⁻¹)	Colour	Dec. temp. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)						λ_M (Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)
				C	H	N	S	O_2^{2-}	U	
1 [$\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBU}(\text{NO}_3)_2$]. H_2O	[$\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_8\text{N}_4$]. H_2O (592.10)	Creamish yellow	290	16.15 (16.22)	1.61 (1.70)	9.40 (9.46)	–	5.37 (5.40)	40.13 (40.20)	4.80
2 [$\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBT}(\text{NO}_3)_2$]. H_2O	[$\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_8\text{N}_4\text{S}$]. H_2O (608.17)	Creamish yellow	280	15.72 (15.80)	1.64 (1.66)	9.15 (9.21)	5.22 (5.27)	5.21 (5.26)	39.08 (39.14)	5.65
3 [$\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBH}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$]. H_2O	[$\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{C}_7\text{H}_8\text{O}_7\text{N}_4$]. H_2O (564.10)	Yellow	> 300	14.82 (14.90)	1.70 (1.79)	9.87 (9.93)	–	5.60 (5.67)	42.13 (42.20)	6.87
4 [$\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBH}_A(\text{NO}_3)_2$]. H_2O	[$\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{N}_3$]. H_2O (565.07)	Light yellow	> 298	14.79 (14.88)	1.58 (1.61)	7.26 (7.44)	–	5.60 (5.66)	42.04 (42.12)	7.85

Table 2. IR spectral data (cm^{-1}) of peroxouranium(VI) complexes

Ligand	$\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{NH}_2)$	$\delta(\text{N-H})$ and $\nu(\text{C-N})$	$\nu(\text{C=O})$ of CONH gp	Complex	$\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{NH}_2)$	$\delta(\text{N-H})$ and $\nu(\text{C-N})$	$\nu(\text{C=O})$ of CONH gp	$\nu(\text{C=S})$	$\nu(\text{U=O})$	$\nu(\text{O-O})$	ν_{asy} (UO_2)	ν_{sym} (UO_2)
NBU	3365, 3190	1408, 1575	1670	1	3410, 3225	1398, 1550	1613	–	958	890	682	469
NBT	3378, 3126	1510, 1570	1690	2	3463, 2998	1458, 1560	1624	1280	980	900	650	463
NBH_2	3470, 3278	1422, 1572	1692	3	3448, 3260	1406, 1522	1623	–	950	906	643	450
NBH_A	3444	1309, 1600	1645	4	3400	1298, 1548	1621	–	980	899	669	441

Table 3. Electronic spectral data (nm) of peroxouranium(VI) complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	λ_{max} (nm)
1.	[$\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBU}(\text{NO}_3)_2$]. H_2O	276, 348, 380
2.	[$\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBT}(\text{NO}_3)_2$]. H_2O	287, 356, 385
3.	[$\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBH}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$]. H_2O	290, 368, 390
4.	[$\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBH}_A(\text{NO}_3)_2$]. H_2O	325, 370, 399

Conductance and magnetic measurements :

The observed molar conductance ($\lambda_M = 4.80\text{--}7.85 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) of all the metal complexes in 10^{-3} molar DMF solution are given in Table 1 which suggest the non-electrolytic nature of these complexes²⁹. All the complexes were found to be diamagnetic as expected for d^0 system of peroxouranium(VI) complexes.

ing (ν_{as}) and symmetric UO_2 stretching (ν_{s}) modes respectively. An additional sharp band at 950–980 cm^{-1} has been assigned to $\nu(\text{U=O})$ mode^{30–32}. In the complexes of the type [$\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBU}(\text{NO}_3)_2$]. H_2O the absorption band around 1613 and 1708 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\nu(\text{CONH})$ and $\nu(\text{CONH}_2)$ stretching vibrations respectively. Both these bands show a negative shift of 15–18 cm^{-1} in the complexes as compared to free ligand showing that carbonyl oxygen atoms are involved in coordination with uranium. Further, the shifting of N–H stretching vibrations of $-\text{NH}_2$ group (3365 cm^{-1}) to higher frequency (3455 cm^{-1}) confirms the bonding of carbonyl oxygen of urea with uranium rather than nitrogen atom of $-\text{NH}_2$ group. The bands in the region 1510–1309 cm^{-1} in case of free ligand can be assigned to $\delta(\text{N-H})$ bending vibrations.

Note

Table 4. Mass spectral data of peroxouranium(VI) complexes

Complex (1)	<i>m/e</i>	M-3*	M*	M+1*	M+2*	Complex (2)	<i>m/e</i>	M-3*	M*	M+1*	M+2*
[UO(O ₂)C ₈ H ₈ O ₈ N ₄].H ₂ O (592.10 g mol ⁻¹)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	[UO(O ₂)C ₈ H ₈ O ₇ N ₄ S].H ₂ O (608.17 g mol ⁻¹)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)
[UO(O ₂)C ₈ H ₈ O ₈ N ₄] ⁺ .H ₂ O	591.10 (100)	0.70	100	10.7	2.9	[UO(O ₂)C ₈ H ₈ O ₇ N ₄ S] ⁺ .H ₂ O	607.17 (100)	0.70	100	11.5	7.3
[UO(O ₂)C ₈ H ₈ O ₈ N ₄] ⁺	573.09 (11.05)	0.70	100	10.6	2.3	[UO(O ₂)C ₈ H ₈ O ₇ N ₄ S] ⁺	589.17 (23.18)	0.70	100	11.4	7.1
[UOC ₈ H ₈ O ₈ N ₄] ⁺	541.09 (28.25)	0.70	100	10.1	1.7	[UOC ₈ H ₈ O ₇ N ₄ S] ⁺	557.19 (9.08)	0.70	100	11.4	6.7
[UOC ₈ H ₈ O ₅ N ₃] ⁺	479.09 (21.25)	0.70	100	9.6	1.0	[UOC ₈ H ₈ O ₄ N ₃ S] ⁺	495.19 (29.54)	0.70	100	11.0	5.8
[UC ₈ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂] ⁺	417.09 (8.03)	0.70	100	9.6	0.8	[UOC ₈ H ₈ ON ₂ S] ⁺	433.19 (22.73)	0.70	100	10.01	5.0
[UC ₈ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂] ⁺	401.10 (26.30)	0.70	100	3.4	0.4	[UOC ₈ H ₈ ON ₂ S] ⁺	417.19 (6.81)	0.70	100	9.80	3.9
[UC ₂ H ₃ O ₂ N ₂] ⁺	324.10 (7.06)	0.70	100	1.5	0.2	[UC ₂ H ₃ N ₂ S] ⁺	340.19 (27.27)	0.70	100	8.08	1.9
[UCONH ₂] ⁺	281.10 (6.06)	-	-	-	-	[UCNH ₂ S] ⁺	297.19 (5.68)	-	-	7.87	0.9
NBU	164.60 (2.27)	100	9.6	0.8		NBT	304.14 (4.54)	-	100	10.09	1.0

*Relative isotopic abundance.

Table 5. *In vitro* efficacy of complexes against *Candida albicans*

Sl. no.	Complexes	Colony diameter (in mm)		%Inhibition	
		$I = [(C - T) \times C]$		at 100 ppm	
		at 200 ppm	at 100 ppm	Ligand Complex	Ligand Complex
1.	[UO(O ₂)NBU(NO ₃) ₂].H ₂ O	25	17	68.75	78.75
2.	[UO(O ₂)NBT(NO ₃) ₂].H ₂ O	28	20	65.00	75.00
3.	[UO(O ₂)NBH _Z (NO ₃) ₂].H ₂ O	30	23	62.50	71.25
4.	[UO(O ₂)NBH _A (NO ₃) ₂].H ₂ O	29	21	63.75	73.75

Colony diameter of control, C = 80 mm.

In the complex [UO(O₂)NBT(NO₃)₂].H₂O, the $\nu(C=S)$ stretching vibrations is observed at 1280 cm⁻¹ indicating a negative shift of 30 cm⁻¹ as compared to free ligand (1310 cm⁻¹) confirming the involvement of thiocarbonyl-sulphur in bonding with uranium. The shifting of $\nu(C=O)$ stretching vibrations of free ligand (1690 cm⁻¹) to lower values in the complexes indicating the involvement of carbonyl oxygen in coordination. The $\nu(NH_2)$ asymmetric stretching appears at 3463 cm⁻¹, where as $\nu(NH_2)$ symmetric stretching appears at 3098 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicating that nitrogen of -NH₂ group is not involved in coordination with uranium.

In the complex [UO(O₂)NBH_Z(NO₃)₂].H₂O, the strong intensity band at 1623 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to $\nu(C=O)$ stretching vibrations as compared to 1692 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand suggesting the involvement of carbonyl oxygen in bonding with uranium. Also, the bands at 3470 and 3278 cm⁻¹, assigned to asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of -NH₂ group in the free ligand also undergo a negative shift of 30-40 cm⁻¹ in the complexes.

Similarly, the $\nu(C=O)$ stretching vibrations of free NBH_A at 1645 cm⁻¹ have found to be shifted to 1621 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, [UO(O₂)NBH_A(NO₃)₂].H₂O confirming the coordination of carbonyl oxygen with uranium. The strong intensity bands at 3400 cm⁻¹ and 1211 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to $\nu(OH)$ stretching and bending vibrations respectively which show a negative shifts compared to free ligand confirming the involvement of hydroxyl oxygen in bonding with uranium.

In these complexes three additional bands which are not present in the spectra of free ligands are observed. Of these a band appears around 1035-1047 cm⁻¹ assigned to bending (ν_2) mode of NO₃ group. Two more bands in the

region 1430–1475 cm^{-1} and 1360–1400 cm^{-1} are assigned as ν_4 and ν_1 modes, respectively, of the coordinated nitrate group. A difference in frequencies between the higher energy bands ($\Delta\nu (\nu_4 - \nu_1) \approx 75 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), suggests unidentate coordination of the nitrate group³³. For bidentate coordination of nitrate group³⁴, the difference should be in the range of 120–180 cm^{-1} .

Thus, IR spectra suggest that in all the complexes the ligands behave in bidentate chelating mode. Also, the presence of lattice water in the complexes was evident from the broad absorption band at 3488 and 3460 cm^{-1} (due to asymmetric OH stretching (ν_{as}) and symmetric OH stretching (ν_s) modes) and a sharp absorption band at 1685–1649 cm^{-1} (due to HOH bending)³⁵.

ESI mass spectral studies :

The ESI mass spectra for the complexes $[\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBU}(\text{NO}_3)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1) and $[\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBT}(\text{NO}_3)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2) show extensive fragmentation and only the most abundant fragment ions with relative isotopic abundance are given in Table 4. The complex 1 displays molecular ion peak at m/e 591.10 for fragment $[\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_8\text{N}_4]^+ \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the complex 2 at m/e 607.17 for fragment $[\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_7\text{N}_4\text{S}]^+ \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. In both the complexes the molecular ion peaks are the base peaks. One more significant peak appears in the mass spectrum at m/e 479.09 corresponding to $[\text{UOC}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_5\text{N}_3]^+$ in complex 1 and m/e 495.19 corresponding to $[\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_4\text{N}_3\text{S}]^+$ in complex 2. The intensities of all the fragments in complex 1 have been represented relative to base peak at m/e 591.10 and for complex 2 relative to base peak at m/e 607.17 (Table 4). Masses of fragment ions listed in table are calculated using uranium atom mass equal to 238.05 amu.

Uranium has two isotopes having atomic masses 235 and 238 amu. Their relative abundances are 0.70% and 100% respectively. Here, the most intense isotope peak is set to 100% and percentages of other isotope peaks are computed relative to it (Table 4). The molecular ion and fragments peaks containing uranium appear in doublet at M^{+*} and $M-3^*$ and ratios of their relative intensities confirm the presence of U-235 and U-238 isotopes in the fragments. In addition $M+1^*$ and $M+2^*$ peaks also appear due to isotopic contribution of C, H, N, O and S atoms.

Electronic spectral studies :

The electronic spectra of the metal complexes were recorded in 10^{-3} M DMF solution (Table 3) in the UV-Visible region. The spectra show three transitions in the range 276–325, 348–370 and 380–399 nm ascribed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ of coordinated nitrate group and the charge transfer transitions from oxygen \rightarrow uranium, i.e. LMCT, $\pi \text{ O}_2^{2-} \rightarrow \text{U}^{36,37}$. There was no evidence of any $d-d$ transition. This result is consistent with the presence of uranium(VI) system in the complexes.

TGA/DTA studies :

TGA and DTA thermogram of representative complex, $[\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBU}(\text{NO}_3)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was recorded in the temperature range from ambient to 1000 $^\circ\text{C}$ in an atmosphere of nitrogen at a heating rate of 10 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. The TGA curve (Fig. 1) for the complex $[\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBU}(\text{NO}_3)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ shows a first weight loss (starting from 30–210 $^\circ\text{C}$) of 8.60% (theoretical weight loss 8.45%) corresponding to outer sphere water molecules and one peroxy group. The DTA curve of the complex shows a sharp endothermic peak at 205 $^\circ\text{C}$ confirming the loss of water molecule. Further heating up to 310 $^\circ\text{C}$ shows a gradual weight loss of 23.44% (theoretical weight loss 23.65%) attributable to loss of two $-\text{NO}_3$ groups an anoxy group. Finally a stable species $[\text{U}(\text{CONH}_2)]$ is formed on heating upto temperature 1020 $^\circ\text{C}$ by a weight loss of 20.60% (theoretical weight loss 20.27%) corresponding to a phenyl and $-\text{CONH}$ group.

Antifungal activity :

The *in vitro* biological screening effects of the investigated compounds in water were tested against the pathogen *Candida albicans* by the poisoned food technique method using Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) nutrient as the medium³⁸. The inoculated plates were incubated at 27 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 6 days. The growth inhibition of *Candida albicans* over control was calculated using the relation :

$$\% \text{ Inhibition } (I) = [(C - T)/C] \times 100$$

where I = percent inhibition, C = growth of fungus in (mm) in control and T = growth of fungus in (mm) in treatment.

The zone of inhibition values in millimeters are presented in the Table 5. It is evident from the table that the metal chelates exhibit higher activity than the free ligands. Antifungal activity of $[\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBT}(\text{NO}_3)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. TGA/DTA thermogram of $[\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBU}(\text{NO}_3)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Fig. 2. Antifungal activity of $[\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{NBT}(\text{NO}_3)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ against *Candida albicans*.

Based on various physico-chemical and spectral studies, it is proposed that the metal : ligand stoichiometric ratio is 1 : 1 in all the complexes. The general compositions of these metal complexes are $[\text{UO}(\text{O}_2)\text{L} \cdot \text{L}(\text{NO}_3)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where L-L = NBU, NBT, NBH_Z and NBH_A). IR spectral studies reveal that the ligands (L-L)

are coordinated to uranium in a bidentate mode through carbonyl oxygen/thiocarbonyl sulphur and nitrogen of $-\text{NH}_2$ group. Electronic spectra suggest d^0 configuration and +6 oxidation state of uranium in these complexes. Magnetic studies reveal diamagnetic nature of complexes thus confirming the +6 oxidation state of uranium. Molar conductance values of complexes indicate that these complexes behave as non-electrolyte. Thermal studies of complexes depict the presence of one water molecule, one peroxy, one oxo and two nitrate group in all these complexes. Antifungal studies show that all the complexes are biologically more active in nature compared to corresponding ligands. On the basis of above facts, following seven coordinated structure is proposed for these complexes :

Experimental

Dimethyl sulphoxide (Ranbaxy), dimethyl formamide (Qualigens), ethanol (commercial) were used after distillation, urea (Rankem), thiourea (NICE), benzoyl chloride (Thomas Baker), dioxane (Qualigens), hydrazine (SDS), hydroxylamine (SRL), NaOH (Himedia), uranyl nitrate (SISCO) and hydrogen peroxide (Merck) were used as supplied. The ligands were prepared by the reported method^{28,39}. The analysis of uranium was carried out gravimetrically as uranyloxinate $\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON})_2\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{ON}$ after decomposing the complex with concentrated nitric acid⁴⁰. Carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulphur were analyzed micro analytically using CHNS analyzer Leco Model-932. The total peroxide content of the complexes was determined by adding a weighed amount of the compound to a cold solution of 1.5% boric acid (w/v) in 0.7 M sulfuric acid (100 ml) and then titrating against standard cerium(IV) solution⁴¹. Molar conductivity of complexes was measured at room temperature by a Digital Conductivity Meter of model 611E having a conductivity cell with a cell constant of $1.0 \pm 10\%$ using 10^{-3} molar solution of complexes in DMF. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by Gouy's method at room temperature using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as standard. IR spectra of complexes over the region $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were recorded on Perkin-Elmer's FTIR spectrophotometer model RX1, using KBr discs. Melting points were determined on Analab melting point apparatus. Mass spectral data were obtained on ESI-esquires 3000 Bruker Daltonics spectrometer. Electronic spectra over the region $200\text{--}900\text{ nm}$ were recorded by UV-Visible single beam spectrophotometer Systronics using 10^{-3} M DMF solution of complexes. TGA/DTA studies were recorded on Linseis STA PT-1000 (Pyris Diamond) thermoanalyser at the heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ per minute in an atmosphere of air in the temperature range $30\text{--}1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Antifungal activities were also carried out against the pathogen *Candida albicans* by the poisoned food technique method.

Preparation of peroxouranium(VI) complexes :

The peroxo complexes were synthesized by reported procedure⁴². In a typical reaction $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 mmol, 0.502 g) was dissolved in methanol. An equimolar (1 mmol) methanolic solution (30 ml) of *N*-benzoyl urea and thiourea related ligand (1 mmol) : NBU (0.164 g), NBT (0.180 g), NBH_2 (0.136 g), NBH_A (0.137 g) was

added to a solution of uranyl nitrate solution followed by addition of potassium hydroxide. The solution was refluxed for 15 min, 10 ml of 30% H_2O_2 was added dropwise and was refluxed for an additional 1 h. The resulting yellow coloured precipitates were filtered after cooling and washed successively with methanol, ether and dried *in vacuo*.

where, L-L = NBU, NBT, NBH_2 and NBH_A .

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